

Precisely Patterned Nanofibers for
High Performance Bioseparations

DELIVERABLE 2.3 PRODUCTION OF ACTIVATED AFFINITY LIGANDS

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Deliverable 2.3 - Production of activated affinity ligands

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation / Acronym	
Mabs	Monoclonal Antibodies
VLPs	Virus Like particles
IgG	Immunoglobulin G
ESI-MS	Mass Spectrometry
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
RT	Room Temperature
HPLC	High-performance liquid chromatography
TFA	Trifluoroacetic acid
WP	Work package

I. Introduction

To target Mabs we selected two synthetic affinity ligands based on different chemical scaffolds (Petasis-Ugi and Triazine) and a biological ligand – *Staphylococcus aureus* protein A. To target Influenza Virus Like particles (VLPs) it was selected Heparin as this ligand is commonly in different commercial platforms.

PURE teams focused focusing on the production of affinity ligands against monoclonal antibodies. Heparin was purchased from an external supplier.

Table I - List of biological targets and affinity ligands used in PURE.

Biological Target	Affinity Ligand	References
Monoclonal antibodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protein A • Triazine synthetic ligand 22/8 • Petasis-Ugi synthetic ligand B1A12A2 • Ugi Ligand A2C711 	[1–4]
Influenza VLPs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heparin 	[5]

2. Ligands targeting Monoclonal Antibodies:

2.1 Biological Ligand – Protein A

The protein A sequence was adapted in existing expression constructs and was expressed in *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) strain BL21(DE3). It was mostly expressed in soluble form in the extracellular fraction (Figure 1). 0.66 µg of protein A was secreted per mL of the extracellular fraction in *E. coli* shake flasks cultures. The protein A was purified *via* affinity chromatography using the IgG 6 Fast Flow resin with covalently coupled human IgG.

The protein was secreted and purified directly from the extracellular fraction of the *E. coli* cultures in shake flasks. It was further isolated and purified using affinity chromatography.

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Figure 1: Coomassie stained 4-12% SDS gels; M, marker showing that protein A occurred predominantly in medium supernatant. The protein A was expressed in *E. coli* BL21(DE3) in shake flask cultures; extracell. TCA, protein A in TCA precipitated medium supernatant. The calculated molecular weight of protein A is 35 kDa.

Figure 2: Coomassie stained SDS gels showing protein A after purification using affinity chromatography. (1, 2, 3) BSA standards ranging from 0.325 µg (1), 0.65 µg (2) to 0.975 µg (3) for quantification; (4) 0.5 µL first fraction and (5) 0.5 µL second fraction of the elution peak of purified protein A; (6) purified protein A; purified protein A. The calculated molecular weight of protein A is 35 kDa. The band at ~28 kDa was unidentified but might be a degradation product.

2.2 Synthetic Ligand 22/8

The solution-phase synthesis of the synthetic ligand 22/8 based on Triazine scaffold was performed using standard protocols already published.[2] The liquid phase synthesis took place through a set of three reactions (Figure 3A). The first reaction occurs at 0°C where the first chlorine of the cyanuric chloride is replaced by a functional group. Then, the second reaction occurs at 45°C where the substitution of the second chlorine occurs. Finally, the third reaction

occurs at 80°C where the last available chlorine is replaced by a functional group. The synthesis was performed in NOVA lab, and the end product was confirmed by Mass Spectrometry (ESI-MS) (Figure 3B) and NMR, however we obtained a low yield (8%).

Figure 3: A) Ligand 22/8 reaction scheme; B) Mass spectrometry spectrum of ligand 22/8 after synthesis.

2.3 Synthetic Ligands

The BIAI2A2 ligand is based on a Petasis-Ugi scaffold developed previously at NOVA.[3] A protocol to synthesize the ligand by liquid-phase synthesis was designed following standard chemical synthesis protocols. The final compound was purified by reverse-phase chromatography in a HPLC system (Agilent) (Figure 4) and characterized by ESI-MS (Figure 5). The chromatogram shows two major peaks which were analysed by ESI-MS. Mass spectroscopy revealed one intense peak with mass/charge ratio (m/z) = 558.2 Da $[M+H]^+$ corresponding to the molecular weight of the soluble BIAI2A2 ligand. The presence of two peaks in the chromatogram indicate isomers of the same molecule.

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Figure 4: Chromatogram of crude ligand using C18 reverse-phase column in a HPLC system (Agilent). After production the B1A12A2 ligand was purified by reverse phase chromatography and eluted with a method with two gradients (purple line): a linear gradient of solvent B (25% to 62% in 15.88min); and an isocratic gradient of solvent B (62% to 80% in 4.12min) at a flow rate of 0.6mL/min (Rt=16.05 and 16.34min, highlighted in the blue box). Solvent A 99.9% Milli-Q® water; 0.1% TFA (Trifluoroacetic acid) and Solvent B 95% Acetonitrile; 4.9% Milli-Q® water; 0.1% TFA.

Figure 5: Mass spectrum of the collected peak after reverse-phase chromatography obtained by ESI-MS. $[M+H]^+ = 558.3$ Da(calculated)/558.2 Da (determined).

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The A2C7II ligand is based on Ugi scaffold developed by El Khoury and Lowe.[4] The synthesis in liquid phase of the new ligand was done following the reference [4]. The compound was purified with reverse-phase chromatography in a HPLC system (Agilent) and characterized by ESI-MS. The A2C7II ligand was obtained as a yellow solid compound in 48% yield (1.67g).

The compound was purified with reverse phase chromatography (Figure 6) and characterized by ESI-MS (Figure 7). Mass spectroscopy revealed one intense peak with mass/charge ratio (m/z) $[M+H]^+ = 499.2$ Da corresponding to the molecular weight of the soluble Petasis-Ugi A2C7II ligand.

Figure 6: Chromatogram of crude ligand using C18 reverse-phase column in a HPLC system (Agilent). After production the A2C7II ligand was purified by reverse phase chromatography and eluted with a method a linear gradient (purple line) of solvent B (25% to 60% in 18min) at a flow rate of 0.6mL/min ($R_t=14.20$ min, highlighted in the blue box). Solvent A 99.9% Milli-Q® water; 0.1% TFA (Trifluoroacetic acid) and Solvent B 95% Acetonitrile; 4.9% Milli-Q® water; 0.1% TFA.

Figure 7: Mass spectrum of the collected peak after reverse-phase chromatography obtained by ESI-MS. $[M+H]^+ = 499.3$ Da (calculated) / 499.2 Da (determined).

3. Summary

BOKU produced about 250 mg of pure protein A.

Regarding synthetic ligands for monoclonal antibodies, three ligands were produced by NOVA team: 22/8 (based on Triazine scaffold), B1A12A2 and A2C711 (both based on Petasis-Ugi scaffold). The ligand 22/8 synthesis was suspended since the reaction is time consuming with a low yield (8%). In contrast, synthetic ligands B1A12A2 and A2C711 (Petasis-Ugi and Ugi scaffolds) easily was obtained 1.5g of crude ligand in a less time-consuming reaction and with an acceptable yield (around 50%). The purification protocol was tested for both ligands with excellent separation, obtaining 250 mg of each purified ligand.

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